
Design of an Integrated Physical Exercise Program and Motivational Strategies in Pediatric Oncologic Rehabilitation

Diseño de un programa integrado de ejercicio físico y estrategias motivacionales en la rehabilitación oncológica pediátrica

Rut López-Osca¹, Ginés D. López-García^{1,2}, Roberto Espinoza-Gutiérrez³
and María Carrasco-Poyatos¹

¹ University of Almería, Almería, Spain, ² ISEM University Centre, Murcia, Spain

³ Autonomous University of Baja California, Tijuana, Mexico

Abstract

Despite growing evidence supporting the benefits of supervised exercise in pediatric oncology, existing interventions exhibit substantial methodological variability, limited standardization, and persistent challenges in sustaining patients' active participation. Although theories such as Self-Determination Theory (SDT) have demonstrated efficacy in promoting autonomous motivation and long-term adherence in clinical contexts, their integration into exercise protocols during pediatric cancer treatment remains largely absent. This article describes the design of a randomized, controlled, crossover trial aimed at implementing a supervised exercise protocol grounded in SDT principles to foster sustained engagement among pediatric oncology patients. The intervention will last a minimum of 12 weeks and be delivered in hospital settings or rehabilitation clinics through group sessions tailored to participants' clinical status and developmental stage. This methodological proposal seeks to address a gap in the literature by integrating physiological and motivational dimensions to optimize adherence and improve therapeutic outcomes in pediatric oncology.

Keywords: Adherence; Pediatric Cancer; Exercise; Clinical Intervention; SDT.

Resumen

A pesar de la creciente evidencia que respalda los beneficios del ejercicio físico en oncología pediátrica, las intervenciones existentes presentan una variabilidad metodológica sustancial, una estandarización limitada y desafíos persistentes para sostener la participación activa de los pacientes. Aunque teorías como la Teoría de la Autodeterminación (SDT) han demostrado eficacia para promover la motivación autónoma y la adherencia a largo plazo en contextos clínicos, su integración en protocolos de ejercicio durante el tratamiento oncológico pediátrico continúa siendo en gran medida inexistente. Este artículo describe el diseño de un ensayo aleatorizado, controlado y cruzado, orientado a implementar un protocolo de ejercicio supervisado fundamentado en principios de la SDT con el fin de fomentar un compromiso sostenido en pacientes de oncología pediátrica. La intervención tendrá una duración mínima de 12 semanas y se llevará a cabo en entornos hospitalarios o clínicas de rehabilitación mediante sesiones grupales adaptadas al estado clínico y a la etapa del desarrollo de los participantes. Esta propuesta metodológica busca abordar una laguna en la literatura mediante la integración de dimensiones fisiológicas y motivacionales para optimizar la adherencia y mejorar los resultados terapéuticos en oncología pediátrica.

Palabras clave: Adherencia; Cáncer pediátrico; Ejercicio físico; Intervención clínica; SDT.

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Correspondence: Ginés David López-García, ISEN University Center, Murcia, Spain
Email: glopez@um.es

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021), approximately 400,000 children and adolescents aged 0-19 are diagnosed with cancer each year, making it one of the leading causes of mortality in childhood (Steliarova-Foucher et al., 2017). Advances in the treatment of cancers in childhood, adolescence, and young adulthood have increased survival rates to roughly 85% (Howlader et al., 2020). However, this improved survival has been accompanied by a substantial burden of chronic and late adverse effects, both physical (e.g., persistent fatigue, muscle atrophy, and functional decline) and psychological (e.g., anxiety, depression, and adjustment difficulties) (Brinkman et al., 2018; Fiuza-Luces et al., 2016). These symptoms are prevalent, rarely occur in isolation, exacerbate the severity of distress experienced, and interfere with the child's ongoing development (Hockenberry & Hooke, 2007).

Pediatric oncology treatments constitute a particularly complex clinical profile in which side effects are interrelated, compromising the physical, functional, and psychosocial dimensions of development (Fiuza-Luces et al., 2016). Somatically, fatigue is among the most prevalent symptoms, presenting in childhood as a generalized sense of weakness and, in adolescence, as persistent physical-mental exhaustion; it often coexists with sleep disturbances, daytime somnolence, and a substantial reduction in physical activity (Hockenberry & Hooke, 2007; Hooke & Linder, 2019). Persistent functional limitations are also observed (e.g., muscle weakness and reduced mobility), along with functional cardiac alterations (e.g., lower cardiorespiratory capacity), all of which are exacerbated by nausea, asthenia, and appetite loss and, consequently, lead to restrictions in activities of daily living such as walking, playing, or climbing stairs (Meacham et al., 2011; Oeffinger et al., 2004; Valenzuela et al., 2025). At the psychosocial level, there is a high prevalence of emotional disorders (e.g., anxiety, depressive symptoms, dysphoria) linked to isolation, treatment-related disturbances in body image, and diagnostic uncertainty (Linder & Hooke, 2019; Cheng et al., 2019; Hong et al., 2023). In this respect, although many patients achieve good adaptation to treatment, a substantial proportion continue to experience persistent psychosocial and physical morbidity, underscoring the need for adjunctive interventions, such as exercise, that facilitate sustained participation from the early phases of treatment.

Given the multidimensional nature of the clinical and psychosocial consequences of childhood cancer, recent evidence recommends combining advanced pharmacological therapies with non-pharmacological interventions to improve symptom control and quality of life (Fiuza-Luces et al., 2016; Fuller et al., 2022; Kreidie, 2020). In this regard, physical exercise has emerged as a low-risk, safe, and feasible adjunct therapy with benefits across physical, symptomatic, and psychosocial domains. Physically, recent meta-analyses and RCTs report increases in strength and functional performance with resistance and endurance programs (Fiuza-Luces et al., 2016; Morales et al., 2018), along with gains in cardiorespiratory fitness and exercise capacity in hospital settings (Saultier et al., 2021; Morales et al., 2018). Symptomatically, reductions in fatigue and greater exercise tolerance have been observed, with subsequent improvements in autonomy for activities of daily living (Huang & Ness, 2011). From a psychosocial perspective, recent studies describe improvements in self-esteem, perceived well-being, and quality of life (Spreafico et al., 2021). Thus, exercise is a low-cost intervention with broad impact; however, its clinical effectiveness depends on sustained participation over time, a core issue addressed explicitly by this protocol. In short, exercise should be considered not merely a complementary intervention but a cross-cutting therapeutic strategy whose effectiveness hinges on early implementation and, crucially, on adopting approaches that foster consistent participation from the beginning through the end of treatment.

Although exercise has been validated as a safe, feasible, and effective intervention in pediatric oncology, its clinical implementation remains marked by substantial methodological heterogeneity, with a notable gap in standardized protocols and guidelines for the reconditioning and rehabilitation of children with cancer (Braam et al., 2016). Intervention durations range from 19 weeks (Fiuza-Luces et al., 2017) to 6 months (Lam et al., 2018; Saultier et al., 2021). Program content also varies: Saultier et al. (2021) include strength, balance, and endurance exercises in addition to sports; Lam et al. (2018)

employ home visits and low-to-moderate-intensity adapted activities; and Fiuza-Luces et al. (2017) implement combined resistance and endurance training. This dispersion in intervention design coupled with wide participant age ranges and heterogeneous diagnoses (e.g., leukemias, lymphomas, solid tumors, and brain tumors) limits comparability and hinders the derivation of robust conclusions (Fiuza-Luces et al., 2017; Lam et al., 2018; Saultier et al., 2021). Methodological heterogeneity is further compounded by the lack of systematic criteria for assessing adherence (e.g., individual adherence thresholds, monitoring mechanisms). For example, Lam et al. (2018) report an 89% attendance rate without specifying compliance with the prescribed dose, whereas Saultier et al. (2021) describe a recruitment refusal rate exceeding 50% and substantial loss to follow-up, but provide no precise data on session-level adherence. This absence of adherence enhancing measures compromises interpretation of the true clinical impact and underscores the need for an integrative approach that couples the physiological rigor of exercise with motivational strategies capable of sustaining active, prolonged participation throughout treatment.

Within the domain of motivational regulation in clinical settings, Self-Determination Theory (SDT; Ryan et al., 2017) offers a robust conceptual framework to sustain active participation in exercise programs (Ng et al., 2012; Fu et al., 2017; Ntoumanis et al., 2025). SDT posits that motivational regulation depends not solely on the intensity of the stimulus but on the extent to which the basic psychological needs for autonomy (feeling agentic in one's decisions), competence (perceiving efficacy and progress), and relatedness (experiencing supportive and meaningful connections) are satisfied (Ryan & Deci, 2020). Need satisfaction fosters autonomous forms of motivation characterized by greater engagement, enjoyment, and behavioral persistence even in clinically adverse contexts (Pinto & Ciccolo, 2010; Xu et al., 2025). In healthcare interventions, positive effects have been reported when motivational principles such as structured choice, informational feedback, peer cooperation, and task meaningfulness are incorporated, thereby cultivating therapeutic climates that internally reinforce participation (Fu et al., 2017; Schmidt-Andersen et al., 2025). Nevertheless, despite growing evidence, formal integration of SDT into exercise protocols for pediatric oncology remains limited. Although recent studies such as Schmidt-Andersen et al. (2025) provide qualitative evidence on motivational determinants in the early phases of treatment, experimental interventions that systematically combine physiological exercise prescription with SDT-grounded motivational strategies have yet to be developed.

Despite advances in recognizing exercise as an adjunct intervention, there remains a gap in the evidence regarding its integration with motivational frameworks in pediatric clinical contexts. To date, only one study has combined an SDT-based motivational framework during pediatric cancer treatment (Schmidt-Andersen et al., 2025). However, that study employed an exploratory qualitative design without experimental implementation or evaluation of clinical outcomes, underscoring the absence of protocols that systematically align the physiological load of exercise with validated motivational principles and reinforcing the need for integrative proposals that address both the physical and psychosocial components of treatment. Accordingly, the objective of the present study is to design a supervised exercise protocol integrating SDT principles to promote sustained participation during oncologic treatment in pediatric populations. We will conduct a 12-week randomized, controlled, crossover trial structured around group-based, play-oriented sessions stratified by age and clinical characteristics. The intervention can be implemented in hospital settings or private clinics (physiotherapy, occupational therapy, exercise training). The protocol has been developed in accordance with the Standard Protocol Items: Recommendations for Interventional Trials (SPIRIT; Chan et al., 2013) and is described following the TIDieR checklist to ensure transparency and replicability (Hoffmann et al., 2014; Sánchez-Martin et al., 2024).

Method

Study Setting

Despite well-documented physical and emotional limitations in this population, and the known benefits of exercise, fewer than 30% of childhood cancer survivors receive rehabilitation services

(Swartz et al., 2022). Accordingly, and based on the literature, training for this population should be approached from a multidimensional perspective that integrates physical exercise, cognitive training, and psychosocial support.

Within the internal organizational framework, two time points or phases are envisaged. The first is the diagnostic phase, spanning from the identification of initial symptoms and the completion of pertinent tests through confirmation of the diagnosis. Upon entering the second phase, the treatment period, a 12-week educational exercise program is offered, which may be extended until school reintegration.

This protocol will be recommended in oncology clinics and is designed to be reproducible in private training and reconditioning centers that include this population; in early childhood, primary, and secondary educational settings, providing clear guidance for classroom teachers and physical education instructors; in hospital rehabilitation units and peripheral centers; in occupational therapy rooms; and even as guidance for parents, guardians, or patient associations.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Regarding inclusion criteria, the protocol is designed for children and adolescents aged 4–18 years, either undergoing oncologic therapy or post-treatment, who score 2–3 on the Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group (ECOG) Performance Status scale (if aged ≥ 12 years) or $\geq 50\%$ on the Lansky Play-Performance Scale (if aged < 12 years). Only children with a medical contraindication or those whose legal guardians do not provide written informed consent will be excluded. No cancer type will be excluded. Discontinuation criteria will apply if participants do not complete 90% of the scheduled sessions, in accordance with the timetable specified in this protocol.

Intervention

To implement this protocol, an exercise professional must be incorporated into the multidisciplinary team, alongside physicians, nurses, physiotherapists, and occupational therapists, who will design and lead the intervention. This will ensure that patients are supervised, monitored, and guided by a specialist at all times, thereby safeguarding protocol safety and optimizing the intervention's efficacy.

Recruited participants will be randomly assigned to an experimental group (Group A), which will undertake an exercise intervention integrating SDT-based strategies, or to a control group (Group B), which will receive only basic physical activity guidelines for home practice. Upon completion of the first training period, a washout phase followed by crossover will be implemented so that all participants receive both conditions over the course of the trial.

The experimental intervention, as described above, will be delivered over 12 weeks, with three sessions per week lasting 45-60 minutes each (Wang et al., 2024). Although extending the intervention and increasing session frequency is recommended, scheduling should be tailored to each child's circumstances, ensuring at least one rest day between sessions and accommodating post-chemotherapy fatigue peaks, particularly 2-4 days after treatment (Hooke & Linder, 2019). Each session will comprise a warm-up, a main component, and a cool-down.

The warm-up will consist of multijoint mobility exercises and preparatory activities for the main segment and/or low-intensity treadmill or stationary cycling, delivered with a playful orientation, for approximately 10 minutes; the cool-down will again include joint mobility and breathing exercises, also lasting about 10 minutes (Saultier et al., 2021). The main segment will be divided into two blocks: a first block of resistance training and a second block of aerobic exercise, each lasting approximately 15-20 minutes (Fiuza-Luces et al., 2017). The resistance block will target upper body, lower body, and core, performing 2-3 sets of 8-15 repetitions per exercise, with 1-2 minutes of rest between sets and exercises (Fiuza-Luces et al., 2017). The aerobic block will comprise games, activities, and exercises designed to enhance cardiorespiratory fitness in a varied manner, incorporating locomotor movements, equipment, music, and cooperative work, at an intensity of roughly 60-70% of maximal heart rate. Full details of the training session structure are provided in Table 1.

Table 1

General structure of a training session

Phase	Time	Intensity	Indications		
Warm-up	5-10'	Borg 2-5	Joint mobility	Hips, shoulders, knees, and spine	
				Mobility games such as Twister or adapted Animal Flow	
				Low-intensity treadmill or stationary bicycle.	
				2–3 sets of 8–15 repetitions, with 1–2 minutes’ rest between sets and exercises	
				Pushing and pulling movements	
			Upper-body exercises	Exercises with resistance bands, balls, ropes or toys, and adapted loads	
	Adapt strength, yoga, balance, and proprioception tasks				
		Lower-body exercises	Hip-dominant and knee-dominant movements		
			Use varied equipment such as resistance bands, boxes/steps, ladders, cones, weights, or toys		
		Aerobic exercises	60–70% of maximal heart rate		
			Games involving locomotion, equipment, music, and cooperative tasks		
Main	30-40'	Borg 5-7	Core	Stability, mobility, and motor control	
				Planks, spinal flexions, cooperative tasks; individualized progression	
			Imagination & symbolism	incorporate narratives, roles, or metaphors to make exercise a meaningful experience	
			Creativity	Offer multiple ways to solve motor challenges and stimulate initiative and autonomy	
			Playful	Flexibility	Adapt to each participant’s needs, pace, and abilities
				Social dimension	Foster cooperation, communication, and sense of belonging
		Implicit learning	Develop physical, cognitive, and emotional skills without perceiving exercise as an obligation		
Cool-down	5-10'	Borg 2-4	Joint mobility	Hip, shoulder, knee, and spine	
			Breathing exercises	Varied breathing rhythms, deep/relaxed breathing, pranayama, pursed-lip breathing, mindful/aware breathing, and playful breathing routines	

The proposed intervention is grounded in a supervised exercise program structured according to SDT principles, designed to facilitate sustained participation during pediatric oncologic treatment. Implementation will occur in small groups (3-5 participants) organized by age, clinical stage, and

similar functional profiles, thereby ensuring individualized training aligned with each patient’s therapeutic phase, physical and emotional status, and medication regimen. In line with SDT, session design and delivery will focus on satisfying three basic psychological needs, autonomy (providing bounded choices and explaining the rationale for tasks), competence (offering informational feedback and positively reinforcing individual progress), and relatedness (fostering cooperative dynamics and supportive bonds among peers and with the professional) (Ryan & Deci, 2017; 2020). Demotivating practices such as social comparison, mismatched task demands, or negative feedback will be avoided due to their adverse impact on behavioral engagement. The motivational climate will be deliberately cultivated through strategies that integrate playful elements, encouraging messages, and the professional’s genuine interest. This approach seeks to shift from a merely prescriptive logic to an exercise experience that is meaningful, self-reinforcing, and clinically sustainable (Morales et al., 2021; Spreafico et al., 2021; Riner & Sellhorst, 2013).

Table 2

SDT-Based Motivational Regulation Applications

Autonomy Feeling empowered to choose and control	Guided options	Offer patients the possibility to choose between 2-3 activities
	Role adjustment	Allow them to take on small roles of responsibility during activities
	Simple explanations	Give understandable reasons for why each exercise is done
	Consider their feelings	Before starting, ask how they feel and adjust the intensity according to your response
Competence Seeing that they are making progress and are capable	Individual progressions	Set challenges tailored to each child
	Achievable goals	Set small, measurable goals
	Positive and informative feedback	Focus on what they do well and how they can improve
	Celebrate visible achievements	Record progress with stickers, bracelets, progress charts. Key to personal improvement, not comparison
Relationship Feeling supported and connected	Cooperative dynamics	Design games where everyone needs to collaborate
	Peer reinforcement	Encourage them to cheer each other on
	Safe spaces	Create rituals for beginning and ending
	Coach empathy	Show genuine interest in the child's life, not just their physical performance.

Instruments

The primary outcome will be motivation toward exercise. Key secondary outcomes will include cardiorespiratory fitness, functional capacity and muscular strength, as well as quality of life and fatigue.

Sport Motivation

The Spanish version of the original Sport Motivation Scale (Pelletier et al., 1995), adapted to physical activity (Sánchez-Oliva et al., 2012), will be used. This instrument comprises 28 items assessing different types of motivation: amotivation (4 items), extrinsic motivation (12 items), and

intrinsic motivation (12 items). Responses are rated on a seven-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree).

Cardiorespiratory Capacity

The Six-Minute Walk Test (6MWT) will be used to assess cardiorespiratory capacity. Grimshaw et al. (2024) show that, in children undergoing acute cancer treatment, the 6MWT is valid, sensitive, and feasible for evaluating physical function. The test consists of walking as far as possible over six minutes on a flat surface—typically a 30-meter corridor—to assess aerobic endurance and functional capacity. In addition, the algorithm proposed by Mizrahi et al. (2019), combined with age, sex, and waist-to-height ratio, will be used to reasonably estimate VO_{2max} in childhood cancer survivors.

Functional Capacity

Functional capacity will be assessed using the 30-s Chair Stand test, also validated for children with cancer by Grimshaw et al. (2024). This test records the number of times a patient can rise from and sit back down on a chair within 30 seconds (McKay et al., 2017).

Quality of Life

Health-related quality of life will be measured using the Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory (PedsQL) validated by Varni et al. (2004). This questionnaire is designed to assess health-related quality of life and disease-specific symptoms in children and adolescents aged 2–18 years. It comprises 18 items across three dimensions, general fatigue, sleep/rest-related fatigue, and cognitive fatigue, and items are scored from 0 to 4, where 0 = “never” and 4 = “almost always” (Varni et al., 2004). This scale is used in clinical research and practice to evaluate fatigue in conditions such as cancer, autoimmune diseases, and chronic fatigue in children (Varni et al., 2004; Yeh et al., 2011).

Adherence

Session completion will be credited when at least 90% of the prescribed exercises are performed. Adherence will be expressed as the percentage of sessions completed relative to the total scheduled, following the criterion used by Fiuza-Luces et al. (2017).

Sample Size

To determine the sample size, RStudio 3.15.0 (PBC, Boston, USA) will be used. The study’s primary variable, motivation toward exercise, will serve as the reference, applying the equation $n = IC^2 \times d^2 / DE^2$. The confidence interval (IC) will be set at 95%, the estimated error (d) at 1, and the standard deviation (SD) for motivation toward exercise will be drawn from prior work by Wilson et al. (2006) and Ng et al. (2012) (SD = 1.22 points). Accordingly, an adequate sample size for the present study is 6 participants per group. The level of significance will be set at $p \leq 0.05$ (Rodríguez-Sabiote et al., 2025).

Recruitment

The sample will be drawn from pediatric oncology patients following diagnosis. Oncologists and nurses will present the training program either in person during oncology visits or by telephone, inviting families to an informational session. During this meeting, children and adolescents with cancer and their legal guardians will be informed about the importance of comprehensive health care, physical and mental, throughout the oncologic process, as well as potential long-term limitations. The positive impact and benefits of exercise programs will be emphasized using appropriate educational methods, and patients will be encouraged to attend training sessions. Information will be provided by the oncologist, physiotherapist, nurse, and an exercise science professional. Patients who agree to participate will be asked to sign written informed consent.

Assignment and Masking

Initial assignment will be performed using block randomization to ensure balance in group size and distribution. The data monitoring committee will execute this process, employing a simple random method, such as a coin toss, to determine the initial group sequence: Group A (Intervention first) and Group B (Control first). After completion of the first period, a crossover design will be

implemented so that participants switch conditions and serve as their own controls. Given the nature of the intervention, participant blinding will not be feasible; however, the investigators responsible for data analysis will remain masked to the assigned sequence to minimize bias.

Figure 1

Diagnosis and treatment timeline, registration schedule, interventions, and assessment in children and adolescents with cancer

Data Analysis

The data monitoring committee will have full access to the final dataset. Data will be analyzed using Jamovi (Jamovi Project 2018, version 0.9.1.7, Sydney, Australia) and RStudio 3.15.0. Prior to analysis, the Shapiro-Wilk test will be conducted to determine the normality of variable distributions. Descriptive data will be presented as mean ± SD and range. All analyses will follow the intention-to-treat principle. If the sample is normally distributed, Student’s t test for independent samples will be used for between-group comparisons at pre-test and post-test, and Student’s paired t test will be used to assess within-group changes. If the sample is nonparametric, the Mann-Whitney U test will be

applied. Standardized mean differences (Cohen's effect size, ES) will be calculated alongside 95% confidence intervals (Hopkins et al., 2009). Associations between variables will be examined using Pearson's correlation coefficient (r); if r exceeds 0.7, the coefficient of determination (r^2) will be used to estimate the percentage of variance in Y relative to X . Statistical significance will be accepted at $p \leq 0.05$.

Supervision

A Data Monitoring Committee (DMC) will be established prior to protocol initiation, composed of investigators with subject-matter expertise. Statistical analyses will be conducted under strict confidentiality. Based on the DMC's recommendations, members of the multidisciplinary intervention team, together with the oncologist, may decide whether to modify a participant's inclusion or continuation in the training program.

An adverse event will be defined as any undesirable medical occurrence affecting a patient, irrespective of the possibility of a causal relationship. Adverse events will be recorded from the time legal guardians sign the informed consent for the child or adolescent; however, events occurring prior to the start of the intervention will not be considered related to the exercise program. Likewise, events arising after completion of the program will not be attributed to the study protocol. In this context, serious adverse events will include loss of consciousness, marked weakness, and acute pain.

Ethics and Dissemination

The study will adhere to the requirements of the Declaration of Helsinki, and approval will be sought from the ethics committees of the University of Almería and the participating hospitals. Informed consent will be obtained from the legal guardians of minors enrolled in the study, who will make decisions on behalf of the children in their care and will be informed of any necessary modifications during the intervention. Confidentiality will be preserved by the Data Monitoring Committee before, during, and after the study, and will be rigorously upheld in the dissemination of findings through scientific journals, social media, and other communication channels. Upon study completion, participating centers will be encouraged to continue offering the motivational exercise program, and participants will be encouraged to maintain attendance

Conclusions

This protocol presents an SDT-based methodological proposal for supervised exercise as a non-pharmacological complement for children with cancer and survivors, grounded in findings from experimental studies and systematic reviews with meta-analyses to date. It adopts an approach that targets all three basic psychological needs through exercise during oncologic care for children and adolescents. This is expected to enhance both physical and mental domains and mitigate late adverse effects, thereby increasing overall treatment effectiveness. Following implementation, we anticipate improvements in adherence; physical outcomes such as functional capacity and muscular strength; cardiorespiratory fitness; health-related quality of life; and fatigue.

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References

- Braam, K. I., van der Torre, P., Takken, T., Veening, M. A., van Dulmen-den Broeder, E., & Kaspers, G. J. (2016). Physical exercise training interventions for children and young adults during and after treatment for childhood cancer. *The Cochrane database of systematic reviews*, 3(3), CD008796. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD008796.pub3>
- Brinkman, T. M., Li, C., Vannatta, K., Marchak, J. G., Lai, J. S., Prasad, P. K., Kimberg, C., Vuotto, S., Di, C., Srivastava, D., Robison, L. L., Armstrong, G. T., & Krull, K. R. (2016). Behavioral, social, and emotional symptom comorbidities and profiles in adolescent survivors of childhood cancer: a report from the childhood cancer survivor study. *Journal of Clinical Oncology*, 34(28), 3417-25. <https://doi.org/10.1200/jco.2016.66.4789>
- Chan, A. W., Tetzlaff, J. M., Gotzsche, P. C., Altman, D. G., Mann, H., Berlin, J. A., Dickersin, K., Hróbjartsson, A., Schulz, K. F., Parulekar, W. R., Krleza-Jeric, K., Laupacis, A., & Moher, D. (2013). SPIRIT 2013 explanation and elaboration: guidance for protocols of clinical trials. *BMJ*, 346, e7586. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.e7586>
- Cheng, L., Liu, F., Feng, S., Wang, Y., Gu, Y., & Kang, Q. (2019). Symptom Experience of Children With Cancer Younger Than Eight Years of Age: An Integrative Review. *Journal of Pain and Symptom Management*, 58(1), 157–166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpainsymman.2019.03.021>
- Fiuza-Luces, C., Padilla, J. R., Soares-Miranda, L., Santana-Sosa, E., Quiroga, J. V., Santos-Lozano, A., Pareja-Galeano, H., Sanchis-Gomar, F., Lorenzo-González, R., Verde, z., López-Mojares, L. M., Lassaletta, A., Fleck, S. J., Pérez, M., Pérez-Martínez, A., & Lucia, A. (2017). Exercise intervention in pediatric patients with solid tumors: the physical activity in pediatric cancer trial. *Medicine and Science in Sport and Exercise*, 49(2), 223-230. <https://doi.org/10.1249/mss.0000000000001094>
- Fu, F., Zhao, H., Tong, F., & Chi, I. (2017). A systematic review of psychosocial interventions to cancer caregivers. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 834. [10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00834](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00834)
- Fuller, C., Huang, H., & Thienprayoon, R. (2022). Managing Pain and Discomfort in Children with Cancer. *Current Oncology Reports*, 24(8), 961–973. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11912-022-01277-1>
- Grimshaw, S. L., Taylor, N. F., Conyers, R., & Shields, N. (2024). Evaluating the measurement properties and feasibility of physical activity and physical function assessments for children undergoing acute cancer treatment. *JSAMS Plus*, 4, Article 100065. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsampl.2024.100065>
- Hockenberry, M., & Hooke, M. C. (2007). Symptom clusters in children with cancer. *Seminars in Oncology Nursing*, 23(2), 152–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soncn.2007.01.001>
- Hoffmann, T. C., Glasziou, P. P., Boutron, I., Milne, R., Perera, R., Moher, D., Altman, D. G., Barbour, V., Macdonald, H., Johnston, M., Lamb, S. E., Dixon-Woods, M., McCulloch, P., Wyatt, J. C., Chan, A. W., & Michie, S. (2014). Better reporting of interventions: template for intervention description and replication (TIDieR) checklist and guide. *BMJ (Clinical research ed.)*, 348, g1687. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.g1687IF>
- Hong, H. C., Min, A., & Kim, Y. M. (2023). A systematic review and pooled prevalence of symptoms among childhood and adolescent and young adult cancer survivors. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 32(9-10), 1768–1794. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.16201>
- Hooke, M. C., & Linder, L. A. (2019). Symptoms in children receiving treatment for cancer-part I: fatigue, sleep disturbance, and nausea/vomiting. *Journal of Pediatric Oncology Nursing*, 36(4):244-261. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1043454219849576>
- Hopkins, W. G., Marshall, S. W., Batterham, A. M., & Hanin, J. (2009). Progressive statistics for studies in sports medicine and exercise science. *Medicine and Science in Sports and Exercise*, 41(1), 3–13. <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0b013e31818cb278>
- Howlander N., Noone A. M., Krapcho M., Miller D., Brest A., Yu M., Ruhl J., Tatalovich Z., Mariotto A., Lewis D.R., Chen H.S., Feuer E.J., Cronin K.A. (2020). *SEER Cancer Statistics Review, 1975-2017*. National Cancer Institute.
- Huang, T. T., & Ness, K. K. (2011). Exercise interventions in children with cancer: a review. *International Journal of Pediatrics*, 2011, 461512. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2011/461512>
- Kreidie, S. A. (2020). *Miracles of comprehensive Non-Pharmacological approaches: An optimized cancer treatment for children*. <https://www.scitechnol.com/peer-review-pdfs/miracles-of-comprehensive-nonpharmacological-approaches-an-optimized-cancer-treatment-for-children-Irzm.pdf>

- Lam, K. K. W., Li, W. H. C., Chung, O. K., Ho, K. Y., Chiu, S. Y., Lam, H. S., & Chan, G. C. F. (2018). An integrated experiential training programme with coaching to promote physical activity, and reduce fatigue among children with cancer: A randomised controlled trial. *Patient Education and Counseling*, *101*(11), 1947–1956. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2018.07.008>
- Linder, L. A., & Hooke, M. C. (2019). Symptoms in Children Receiving Treatment for Cancer-Part II: Pain, Sadness, and Symptom Clusters. *Journal of Pediatric Oncology Nursing: Official Journal of the Association of Pediatric Oncology Nurses*, *36*(4), 262–279. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1043454219849578>
- McKay, M. J., Baldwin, J. N., Ferreira, P., Simic, M., Vanicek, N., Burns, J., & 1000 Norms Project Consortium (2017). Reference values for developing responsive functional outcome measures across the lifespan. *Neurology*, *88*(16), 1512–1519. <https://doi.org/10.1212/WNL.0000000000003847>
- Meacham, L. R., Chow, E. J., Ness, K. K., Kamdar, K. Y., Chen, Y., Yasui, Y., Oeffinger, K. C., Sklar, C. A., Robison, L. L., & Mertens, A. C. (2011). Cardiovascular risk factors in adult survivors of pediatric cancer - a report from the childhood cancer survivor study. *Cancer Epidemiology, Biomarkers & Prevention*, *19*(1), 170-181. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-09-0555>
- Mizrahi, D., Fardell, J. E., Cohn, R. J., Partin, R. E., Howell, C. R., Hudson, M. M., Robison, L. L., Ness, K. K., McBride, J., Field, P., Wakefield, C. E., & Simar, D. (2020). The 6-minute walk test is a good predictor of cardiorespiratory fitness in childhood cancer survivors when access to comprehensive testing is limited. *International Journal of Cancer*, *147*(3), 847–855. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijc.32819>
- Morales, J. S., Valenzuela, P. L., Rincón-Castanedo, C., Takken, T., Fiuza-Luces, C., Santos-Lozano, A., & Lucia, A. (2018). Exercise training in childhood cancer: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Cancer Treatment Reviews*, *70*, 154–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctrv.2018.08.012>
- Morales, J., Valenzuela, P., Velázquez-Díaz, D., Castillo-García, A., Jiménez-Pavón, D., Lucia, A., & Fiuza-Luces, C. (2021). Exercise and childhood cancer - a historical review. *Cancers*, *14*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers14010082>
- Ng, J. Y. Y., Ntoumanis, N., Thøgersen-Ntoumani, C., Deci, E. L., Ryan, R. M., Duda, J. L., & Williams, G. C. (2012). Self-Determination Theory Applied to Health Contexts: A Meta-Analysis. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, *7*(4), 325-340. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691612447309>
- Ntoumanis, N., & Moller, A. C. (2025). Self-determination theory informed research for promoting physical activity: Contributions, debates, and future directions. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 102879. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2025.102879>
- Oeffinger, K. C., & Hudson, M. M. (2004). Long-term complications following childhood and adolescent cancer: foundations for providing risk-based health care for survivors. *A Cancer Journal for Clinicians*, *54*(4), 208-36. <https://doi.org/10.3322/canjclin.54.4.208>
- Organización Mundial de la Salud. (2021). *CureAll framework: WHO global initiative for childhood cancer: increasing access advancing quality, saving lives*. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240025271>
- Organización Mundial de la Salud. (2021). *El Cáncer Infantil*. <https://www.who.int/es/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cancer-in-children>
- Pelletier, L. G., Tuson, K. M., Fortier, M. S., Vallerand, R. J., Briere, N. M., & Blais, M. R. (1995). Toward a new measure of intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and amotivation in sports: The Sport Motivation Scale (SMS). *Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, *17*(1), 35-53. <https://doi.org/10.1123/jsep.17.1.35>
- Pinto, B. M., Ciccolo, J. T. (2010). Physical Activity Motivation and Cancer Survivorship. In: Courneya, K., Friedenreich, C. (eds) *Physical Activity and Cancer. Recent Results in Cancer Research*, vol 186. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-04231-7_16
- Riner, W., & Sellhorst, S. (2013). Physical activity and exercise in children with chronic health conditions. *Journal of Sport and Health Science*, *2*:12-20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JSHS.2012.11.005>
- Rodríguez-Sabiote, C., Vázquez, L. M., López-López, J. A., & Sánchez-Martín, M. (2025). Effect size as an alternative to statistical significance testing. A practical example with JASP. *Espiral. Cuadernos del Profesorado*, *18*(38), 129-141. <https://doi.org/10.25115/ecp.v18i38.10234>
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2017). *Self-determination theory. Basic Psychological Needs in Motivation, Development, and Wellness*. The Guilford Press.

- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2020). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation from a self-determination theory perspective: definition, theory, practices, and future directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology, 61*, 101860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101860>
- Sánchez-Martín, M., Olmedo Moreno, E. M., Gutiérrez-Sánchez, M., & Navarro-Mateu, F. (2024). EQUATOR-Network: a roadmap to improve the quality and transparency of research reporting. *Espiral. Cuadernos del Profesorado, 17*(35), 108-116. <https://doi.org/10.25115/ecp.v17i35.9529>
- Sánchez-Oliva, D., Leo, F. M., Amado, D., González-Ponce, I., & García-Calvo, T. (2012). Desarrollo de un cuestionario para valorar la motivación en educación física. *Revista Iberoamericana de Psicología del Ejercicio y el Deporte, 7*(2), 227-250. <http://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=311126611010>
- Saultier, P., Vallet, C., Sotteau, F., Hamidou, Z., Gentet, J. C., Barlogis, V., Curtillet, C., Verschuur, A., Revon-Riviere, G., Galambrun, C., Chambost, H., Auquier, P., Michel, G., & André, N. (2021). A Randomized Trial of Physical Activity in Children and Adolescents with Cancer. *Cancers, 13*(1), 121. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers13010121>
- Schmidt-Andersen, P., Boensvang, N. N., Pouplier, A., Lykkedegn, S., Hasle, H., Müller, K., J. Christensen, M. K. Fridh, H. B. Larsen (2025). Exploring Motivation for Engaging in Exercise During the First Six Months of Childhood Cancer Treatment: A Qualitative Study. *European Journal of Cancer Care, 2025*(1), 8305173. <https://doi.org/10.1155/ecc/8305173>
- Sharp, K. M. H., Lindwall, J. J., Willard, V. W., Long, A. M., Martin-Elbahesh, K. M., & Phipps, S. (2017). Cancer as a stressful life event: Perceptions of children with cancer and their peers. *Cancer, 123*(17), 3385–3393. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cncr.30741>
- Spreafico, F., Barretta, F., Murelli, M., Chisari, M., Gattuso, G., Terenziani, M., Ferrari, A., Veneroni, L., Meazza, C., & Massimino, M. (2021). Positive impact of organized physical exercise on quality of life and fatigue in children and adolescents with cancer. *Frontiers in Pediatrics, 9*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fped.2021.627876>
- Steliarova-Foucher, E., Colombet, M., Ries, L. A. G., Moreno, F., Dolya, A., Bray, F., Hesselting, P., Shin, H. Y., Stiller, C. A., & IICC-3 contributors. (2017). International incidence of childhood cancer, 2001-10: a population-based registry study. *The Lancet. Oncology, 18*(6), 719-731. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1470-2045\(17\)30186-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1470-2045(17)30186-9)
- Swartz, M. C., Kelly, D. M., Schadler, K. L., Andersen, C. R., Wells, S. J., Zhang, S., Rajan, A., Heaton, A., & Moody, K. (2022). System-level barriers and facilitator to cancer rehabilitation delivery for children with cancer. *Journal of Clinical Oncology, 40*(28 suppl), 81-81. https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2022.40.28_suppl.081
- Valenzuela, P. L., Morales, J. S., Santana-Sosa, E., Velasco, B. H., Baño-Rodrigo, A., Ramos, E. S., Santos-Lozano, A., Lucia, A., Carmen Fiuza-Luces (2025). Physical fitness and cardiac function in childhood cancer survivors. *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2025.05.009>
- Varni, J. W., Burwinkle, T. M., & Szer, I. S. (2004). The PedsQL multidimensional fatigue scale in pediatric rheumatology: reliability and validity. *The Journal of Rheumatology, 31*(12), 2494-500. <https://www.jrheum.org/content/31/12/2494.tab-references>
- Wang, S., Li, M., Wu, Y., Guan, Q., & Zhang, R. (2024). Effects of exercise interventions on cancer-related fatigue in children with cancer: a meta-analysis. *World on Evidence-Based Nursing, 21*(6), 678-686. <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12742>
- Wilson, P. M., Blanchard, C. M., Nehl, E., & Baker, F. (2006). Predicting physical activity and outcome expectations in cancer survivors: an application of Self-Determination Theory. *Psycho-Oncology: Journal of the Psychological, Social and Behavioral Dimensions of Cancer, 15*(7), 567-578. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pon.990>
- Xu, Z., Shamsulariffin, S., Azhar, Y., & Xi, M. (2025). Does Self-Determination Theory Associate With Physical Activity? A Systematic Review of Systematic Review. *International Journal of Psychology, 60*(3), e70044. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijop.70044>
- Yeh, C. H., Wai, J. P. M., Lin, U. S., & Chiang, Y. C. (2011). A pilot study to examine the feasibility and effects of a home-based aerobic program on reducing fatigue in children with acute lymphoblastic leukemia. *Cancer Nursing, 34*(1), 3-12. [10.1097/NCC.0b013e3181e4553c](https://doi.org/10.1097/NCC.0b013e3181e4553c)